

GROWTH INDICATORS AND OVERALL CONDITION OF EASTERN BIOTA (*PLATIGLADUS ORIENTALIS S.*) IN GREENING THE STREETS AND HIGHWAYS OF NUKUS CITY

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Abstract. *This study examines the growth indicators and overall condition of Eastern Biota (*Platigladus orientalis S.*) species utilized in greening the streets and highways of Nukus city. The research focuses on the species' adaptability and resilience in urban environments, evaluating key parameters such as height, trunk diameter, and foliage health.*

Through systematic observation and data collection, the study aims to assess how effectively these trees thrive under local environmental conditions, including soil quality, water availability, and climatic influences. The findings highlight the significant role of Eastern Biota in enhancing the aesthetic appeal and ecological integrity of urban landscapes.

Keywords. *Eastern Biota (*Platigladus orientalis S.*), greening, growth indicators, overall condition, Nukus city, highways, streets, urban environment, adaptation, resilience to resources, natural resources, biodiversity, aesthetic enhancement, recent findings, research process.*

Introduction

The address delivered by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirmonovich Mirziyoev, at the 75th session of the United Nations General Assembly was widely acclaimed by not only the people of Uzbekistan but also the global community. His speech put forward a number of concrete proposals and initiatives aimed at tackling a broad spectrum of pressing issues. Notably, for the first time in history, our President delivered his speech in Uzbek from the UN's highest podium, filling the entire nation with pride and a profound sense of accomplishment.

In this speech, the President once again focused international attention on several urgent matters, among them the dire ecological situation in the Aral Sea region, specifically highlighting the ongoing Aral Sea disaster. The Aral Sea crisis stands as one of the most significant global ecological catastrophes of our time. Its far-reaching environmental, socio-economic, and humanitarian consequences directly threaten the sustainable development of the region, public health, and the genetic diversity and future of its inhabitants, while also exerting a negative impact on the global ecosystem. The Aral Sea crisis zone primarily affects the territories of Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan, with secondary effects reaching into Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan.

According to expert assessments, a new saline desert has emerged on the dried-up seabed of the Aral Sea, spanning an area of approximately 5.5 million hectares. In this region, dust storms occur for more than 90 days each year, lifting over 100 million tons of dust and toxic salts into the atmosphere and spreading them across vast distances.

This ecological catastrophe has profound implications not only for the region but also for global environmental health. Dust and pollutants from the Aral Sea have been detected thousands of kilometers away, affecting ecosystems, agriculture, and human health far beyond Central Asia. The toxins, heavy metals, and salt particles carried by winds exacerbate respiratory diseases, threaten biodiversity, and contribute to soil degradation across the region.

In light of these challenges, reducing the negative impact of the Aral Sea crisis on both the environment and the livelihoods of people in the surrounding areas, as well as mitigating further climate-related deterioration, represents one of the most pressing tasks facing the international community. Immediate action is needed to alleviate the suffering of the affected populations and to restore ecological balance in the region. This issue is of global significance and requires coordinated international efforts to develop and implement comprehensive solutions.

Research Methodology. In the surroundings of Nukus city, Republic of Karakalpakstan, a comprehensive study was conducted on the phenology of local and introduced tree species during the vegetation period, along with their aesthetic value and growth indicators. The trees' resilience to the local climate and soil conditions, wood structure, and the quality of seeds were evaluated based on a selection assessment method using a 6-point scale.

Seasonal phenomena were closely observed by monitoring the growth of trees and shrubs in different seasons. These observations were carried out at one or more geographical locations to determine the duration of various phenological phases. Monitoring the developmental stages of trees helps in understanding their biological cycles and adaptability to climatic conditions, providing essential information for determining the appropriate planting strategies and management of these species.

The knowledge gained from these seasonal observations plays a significant role, especially in agriculture and forestry. The findings are critical for determining which tree species are suitable for specific climates and how best to utilize them. This is particularly valuable in species zoning and afforestation planning.

To study the life cycles of trees and shrubs and their seasonal phenomena, the following observations were conducted:

- The beginning of sap flow in tree trunks;
- Swelling of leaf and flower buds;
- Full leaf unfolding;
- The start and complete yellowing of leaves;
- Leaf shedding;
- The start of flowering and full bloom;
- The onset of fruit and seed ripening;
- The final ripening of fruits and seeds;
- The beginning of fruit and seed shedding.

The results of these observations were recorded in special tables. Periodic monitoring of the experimental plots, where the main trees and shrubs were planted, was conducted. At the beginning of each year, phenological observations were carried out, and the data obtained was systematically recorded in the designated observation tables.

The obtained results and their analysis. In the tranquil recreation areas of Nukus city, the Eastern Biota (*Platigladus orientalis* S.) stands out as a dominant species among coniferous trees (1-figure). This remarkable plant can reach a height of up to 10 meters and is renowned for its aesthetic appeal and vital ecological functions, as well as its numerous beneficial characteristics for urban environments.

The trunk of the Eastern Biota is covered with dark gray bark, which peels off as the tree matures. Its branches form a striking pyramidal shape, consisting of vertically growing twigs. These twigs are flat, firm, and display a vibrant green color, enhancing the plant's overall visual

appeal. The leaves are needle-like and scale-like, with sharp tips, glandular structures, and a translucent green hue that emphasizes their uniqueness.

The Eastern Biota primarily reproduces through seeds but can also be easily propagated through cuttings. This species has a slow growth rate, necessitating patience and attention during its care. It is shade-tolerant, heat-loving, and drought-resistant, capable of withstanding cold and pollution from gases as it matures. While it can thrive in various soil types, it particularly flourishes in calcareous sandy soils, which provide optimal conditions for growth. Its root system is notably robust, allowing the plant to anchor securely in the ground.

Figure 1: General view of the Eastern Biota trees along the streets and highways of Nukus city.

The branches of the Eastern Biota are flexible, enabling them to resist damage from strong winds and heavy snowfall. There are various forms of the plant that exhibit dense, round canopies and gracefully arching growth patterns. Some of these trees appear compact, while others grow tall, showcasing shades of green, bluish, and off-white.

The Eastern Biota is widely distributed in the mountainous regions of Northern China and along the banks of the Topalang River in the Hisor Mountains. It also thrives in cities and parks in the southern regions of the CIS, contributing to its urban adaptability. It is recommended to plant this species either individually or in groups for landscape beautification purposes. In Tashkent, it is cultivated extensively and used widely for urban greening projects, further enhancing its popularity.

The Eastern Biota, with its aesthetic charm and adaptability to different climatic conditions, plays a significant role in creating beauty and tranquility in the recreation areas of Nukus. This plant not only contributes to the visual aesthetics of the city but also plays a crucial role in improving the urban ecosystem. Its presence enriches the landscape and offers a calming environment for residents and visitors alike.

Through its integration into the urban landscape, the Eastern Biota aids in enhancing the quality of life in Nukus city by providing green spaces that promote relaxation and well-being. It

serves as a vital component in the efforts to maintain sustainable and attractive urban environments, supporting both ecological integrity and the health of the community.

Selection of Eastern Biota Seedlings for Greening Purposes

Selecting the right local and introduced tree and shrub seedlings for greening purposes is crucial for ensuring ecological sustainability and improving the urban environment. In this context, seedlings of the Eastern Biota were planted in the specialized state forestry nurseries of Nukus.

During the research process, 30 seedlings from each species were planted. These seedlings were measured for various traits, and the results were recorded in tables. The aim of this study was to determine the growth dynamics of the planted seedlings, their health, and their adaptability to the environment.

In 2020, the biometric indicators of the Eastern Biota seedlings showed that their average height was 51.3 cm, while the diameter of the root collar was 0.6 cm (Table 1). These indicators provide important information regarding the growth process of the seedlings, which is influenced by the growing conditions and care methods applied.

Moreover, the results of this study can serve as a foundation for developing more effective strategies in greening practices. They can help optimize the development of plants and contribute to enhancing the beauty and ecological sustainability of urban landscapes in the future.

Overall, the planting of Eastern Biota seedlings and their biometric indicators represent a significant step in greening the city, preserving natural beauty, and restoring ecological balance.

Table 1

Growth Indicators of Eastern Biota Used in Greening (cm)
(Nukus Specialized State Forestry, 2023)

№	Tree-Shrub Species	Quantity	Age	Height (cm)	Diameter (cm)
1.	Eastern Biota	30	3	51,3±1,3	0,6±0,1

Observations on Eastern Biota Seedlings

In our observations conducted in 2024, we focused on studying the phenology, height and diameter growth, environmental resilience, and overall condition of 4-year-old Eastern Biota seedlings throughout the growing season. This comprehensive study aimed to evaluate how these seedlings adapt to external environmental conditions and their capacity for growth and development under varying circumstances.

During the research, we monitored various factors influencing the seedlings, including climatic conditions, soil quality, and potential pests or diseases. We aimed to gather detailed data on their growth patterns, measuring both height and diameter, to assess their overall health and vigor.

Table 2

Growth Indicators of Eastern Biota Used in Greening (cm)
(Nukus Specialized State Forestry, 2024)

№	Tree-Shrub Species	Quantity	Age	Height (cm)	Diameter (cm)
1.	Eastern Biota	30	4	66,1±1,2	0,9±0,2

Additionally, the study sought to understand the phenological phases of the Eastern Biota, observing key stages such as budding, leaf expansion, flowering, and any signs of stress due to environmental factors. The resilience of these seedlings to adverse conditions, such as drought or extreme temperatures, was also a critical aspect of our analysis.

The findings from this research are essential for informing future greening initiatives and improving planting strategies for Eastern Biota in urban and rural landscapes. The results will be summarized in Table 2, highlighting key indicators of growth and health throughout the growing season.

Growth Observations of *Platyladus orientalis* Seedlings

During the course of our observations, it became evident that among the coniferous species, the *Platyladus orientalis* seedlings planted in 2020 demonstrated remarkable growth patterns. By the year 2023, these seedlings had reached an impressive height of 51.3 cm, reflecting their adaptation to the local environment and the effectiveness of the cultivation techniques employed.

However, the most striking observation was noted in 2024, when the height of these seedlings increased significantly to 66.1 cm. This growth of 14.8 cm within a single year underscores not only the vigor of the species but also the positive influence of favorable environmental conditions, such as adequate moisture, optimal soil composition, and appropriate sunlight exposure.

The consistent growth rate observed in the *Platyladus orientalis* seedlings highlights their resilience and ability to thrive in the face of varying environmental factors. This species appears to be well-suited for urban greening initiatives, where it can contribute to enhancing biodiversity and improving the aesthetic quality of green spaces.

Moreover, the data collected from these observations will be instrumental in refining future planting strategies and maintenance practices. Understanding the growth dynamics of Eastern Biota seedlings is essential for maximizing their health and development, ensuring that they can flourish in various ecological settings.

These findings not only contribute to the body of knowledge regarding coniferous species but also provide valuable insights for environmentalists and urban planners focused on sustainable greening practices.

Conclusion: The research results indicate that the locally grown and introduced tree species around the city of Nukus exhibit varying levels of adaptation to the local climate and soil conditions. Observing the phenology of trees, i.e., their seasonal development processes, plays a crucial role in determining which species are suitable for cultivation under specific climatic and soil conditions. Additionally, this process is significant in evaluating the aesthetic and agricultural qualities of trees, including the quality of their wood and the ripening stages of their seeds.

Phenological observations reveal that the growth processes of trees and shrubs go through various developmental stages during the seasons. These observations help identify how trees adapt to different climatic conditions, their life stages, and biological changes, providing a scientific basis for future greening and afforestation projects.

The findings confirm that, depending on the specific climatic conditions and the characteristics of planting areas, using different species ensures the successful propagation of trees and supports sustainable development efforts.

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